

INC 2005

Organised by the Computer and Communications Systems Laboratory,
University of the Aegean and the
Network Research Group, University of Plymouth

Programme

Overview

Monday 4th July, 2005	Registration (from 18:00) Welcome reception/cocktails
Tuesday 5th July, 2005	Registration (from 08:30) Opening ceremony Paper presentations Barbeque
Wednesday 6th July, 2005	Paper presentations Conference dinner & tour
Thursday 7th July 2005	Paper presentations Closing session

Social Events

Monday 4th July, 2005 – Welcome reception/cocktails
Conference venue, 7pm

Tuesday 5th July, 2005 – Barbeque
Conference venue, 8pm

Wednesday 6th July, 2005 – Conference dinner & Tour
Tour at 6pm, dinner at 8.30pm (Pyrgos Village)

**Please ensure your mobile phone / pager /
watch alarms are turned off during the
conference sessions.**

Tuesday 5th July 2005

09:00 Introduction and welcome to INC 2005

Steven Furnell & Sokratis Katsikas, Conference Co-Chairs & Georgios Kormentzas, Programme Co-Chair

Keynote - Ian Akyildiz, Georgia Tech University, USA, "Wireless Sensor Networks"

Coffee/Tea Break

Hall One

Session 1 : Networks [10:30 - 12:35]

Chair: Michael Paterakis

Traffic classification using Self-Organizing Maps
U. Payer, P. Teufl and M. Lamberger (Austria)

Enhanced Class-based Fair Queuing Scheme for Ethernet Passive Optical Network
B. Burentugs, S.Y. Lee and H.S. Park (Korea)

Performance Analysis of the Optical Burst Switching System with Completely Isolated Classes
S.Y. Lee, I.Y. Hwang and H.S. Park (Korea)

Choosing A Deterministic Function For Use With DAOMAP, the Distributed Allocation Of Multicast Addresses Protocol
M.L. Slaviero and M.S. Olivier (South Africa)

Offloading Multimedia Proxies using Network Processors
Ø. Hvamstad, C. Griwodz and P. Halvorsen (Norway)

Hall Two

Session 1 : Mobility [10:30 - 12:35]

Chair: Dimitris Vergados

Performance of a Java-based Mobile 3-tier PACS Application for DICOM compliant Medical Images over Heterogeneous Radio Networks
C. Doukas, V. Moulos, I. Maglogiannis and G. Kormentzas (Greece)

Virtual Anchor based Localization method for Wireless Sensor Networks
J.Y. Choi, H.S. Park, W.H. Kwon, J.J. Kim, Y.H. Kim and Y.H. Shin (Korea)

Real-time Localization for Wireless Sensor Networks with multiple beacon transmissions
G.S. Paschos, E.D. Vagenas and S.A. Kotsopoulos (Greece)

Lunch Break – LOCATION

Session 2 : Security [14:00 - 15:40]

Chair : Udo Bleimann

Enhancing Security Policy Negotiation in the Grid
L. Gymnopoulos, V. Tsoumas, I. Souplonis and S. Gritzalis (Greece)

MBMAEC: a New Protocol for Multicast Authentication using Erasure Codes in Adversarial Networks
H.K. Aslan (Egypt)

A Security Infrastructure for Cross-Domain Deployment of Script-Based Business Processes in SOC Environments
K.P. Fischer, U. Bleimann, W. Fuhrmann and S.M. Furnell (Germany, UK, Australia)

Session 2 : Special Session [14:00 - 15:40]

Performance Modelling and Evaluation of Heterogeneous IP-based Communication Systems
Chair : Harry Skianis

Performance of Broadband Multihop Networks with Cooperative Diversity over Fading Channels
G.K. Karagiannidis, T.A. Tsiftsis and S.A. Kotsopoulos (Greece)

Evaluating the behaviour of Peer-to-Peer IP traffic in wireless access networks
D. Astuti and M. Kojo (Finland)

On the Performance of a Collision Avoidance Protocol with New Backoff Retransmission Mechanism in Multihop Ad-Hoc Networks
J. Atzarakis and M. Paterakis (Greece)

An Investigation of Common and Dedicated channel assignment for efficient support of Multicast services in UMTS networks
G. Koltsidas, G. Dimitriadis and F.N. Pavlidou (Greece)

Coffee/Tea Break

Session 3 : Mobility [16:20 - 18:00]

Chair : TBD

Using compatible keys in achieving subscriber privacy channelling for billing in GSM Networks
N.J. Croft and M.S. Olivier (South Africa)

Performance Analysis of Bluetooth Piconets Under Mutual Interference Using Bit Error Rate
S.Y. Shin, H.S. Park, W.H. Kwon, J.J. Kim, Y.H. Kim and Y.H. Shin (Korea)

Service Architecture for an object-oriented next generation profile register
A. Diehl, U. Bleimann, W. Fuhrmann, P. Reynolds and S. Rupp (Germany, UK)

Session 3 : Special Session [16:20 - 18:00]

Performance Modelling and Evaluation of Heterogeneous IP-based Communication Systems

Chair : Harry Skianis

Can Active Networking Improve the Traffic Profile of Distributed Virtual Environments
T. Balikhina, D. Duce, A. Maqousi and F. Ball (UK, Jordan)

Channel Allocation Handoff Schemes for Cellular Wireless Networks: an overview
D.D. Vergados, A. Sgora, I. Maglogiannis and I. Anagnostopoulos (Greece)

4G Wireless Networks with a GPS Traffic Handling Scheme: Performance Modelling and Evaluation
D. Kouvatso, I. Awan and Y. Li (UK)

Analysis of H.264 video encoded traffic
H. Koumaras, C. Skianis, G. Gardikis and A. Kourtis (Greece)

20:00 Barbeque (conference venue)

Wednesday 6th July 2005

09:00 Keynote - Hamid Asgari, TRT, UK, "Inter-Provider QoS-based Service Offering"

Coffee/Tea Break

Hall One

Session 1 : Networks [10:30 - 12:35]
Chair : Hamid Asgari

ROME: Optimising DHT-based Peer-to-Peer Networks
J. Salter and N. Antonopoulos (UK)

HANA: A Hybrid Active Network Architecture
X. Shao and T. Tokuda (Japan)

SCTP extensions for time sensitive traffic
V. Basto and V. Freitas (Portugal)

Reducing Processing Latency in Network Packet Filters
V. Grout, J. McGinn and J. Davies (UK)

Analysis of Load Balancing in a Beowulf Cluster
D. Adams and D. Finkel (USA)

Hall Two

Session 1 : Security [10:30 - 12:10]
Chair: Sokratis Katsikas

Markov Model for Polymorphic Shellcode Detection
U. Payer and S. Kraxberger (Austria)

A New Technique for Testing Buffer Overflow Vulnerabilities in C and C++
S. Alouneh and A. En-Nouaary (Canada)

Delegation Perspective of Practical Authorization Schemes
I. Agudo, J. Lopez, J.A. Montenegro, E. Okamoto and E. Dawson (Spain, Japan, Australia)

A new perspective on Risk Assessment Techniques
E. Smith and J.H.P. Eloff (South Africa)

SIP Security Mechanisms: A state-of-the-art review
D. Geneiatakis, G. Kambourakis, T. Dagiuklas, C. Lambrinouidakis and S. Gritzalis (Greece)

Lunch Break – LOCATION

Session 2 : Applications [14:00 - 16:05]
Chair : Mariki Eloff

Off-line Karma: A Decentralized Currency for Static Peer-to-peer and Grid Networks
F.D. Garcia and J-H. Hoepman (The Netherlands)

Business Model: a theoretical concept or a necessary business tool?
E. Tavlaki and E. Loukis (Greece)

Smart-project: A Multi-Agent System to support online student group projects
M. Bousmah, N. Elkamoun and A. Berraissoul (Morocco)

DIVITOR Client/Server Application (DIgitalization, VIsualisation and Treatment in ORthodontics)
D. Goularas, K. Djemal, Y. Manoussakis and C. Cosenza (France)

Balancing patient privacy and treatment facility accountability using a centralised pseudonymous HIV/AIDS database
H.S. Venter, M.S. Olivier, J.H.P. Eloff and M.E. Botes (South Africa)

Session 2 : Special Session [14:00 - 16:05]
Digital Switchover and Spectrum Dividend:
Chair : Evangelos Palis

Adaptive bandwidth sharing policies for IP over DVB traffic
D. Negru, A. Mehaoua and E. Pallis (France, Greece)

Digital switchover in UHF: Supporting tele-learning applications over the ATHENA platform
G. Mastorakis, V. Zacharopoulos, A. Sideris, E. Marakakis and A. Fatsea (Greece)

Facts and trends in the evolution of digital broadcasting in Romania
O. Fratu, I. Ioniță, A. Furtună and S. Halunga (Romania)

Interactive TV: Roadmap to convergence
D. Florescu, J.M. Hasemann and S. Moczarski (Germany)

Dynamic bandwidth management system simulator
M. Bucur, R. Cacoveanu and S. Ciochina (Romania)

19:00 Conference Dinner & Tour
Tour from 18:00, Dinner at 20:30

Thursday 7th July 2005

Hall One

Session 1 : Networks [09:00 - 10:15]
Chair : Angelos Rouskas

On the Evaluation of VoIP Perceived QoS for low-bit rate voice codecs
T. Dagiuklas and G. Papazafiriou (Greece)

Performance of Adaptive Multimedia Transmission: The case of Unicast Technique
C. Bouras and A. Gkamas (Greece)

An Open Distributed Software System for Providing Traffic Control and Resource Management Functionality in Heterogeneous ATM Core Networks
K. Katzourakis, G. Kormentzas, K. Kontovasilis and C. Efstathiou (Greece)

Hall Two

Session 1 : Security [09:00 - 10:15]
Chair : Kostas Lambrinouidakis

Using Human Computer Interaction principles to promote usable security
D. Katsabas, S.M. Furnell and P.S. Dowland (UK, Australia)

Artificial Impostor Profiling for Keystroke Analysis on a Mobile Handset
J. Lecomte, N.L. Clarke and S.M. Furnell (UK, Australia)

Autonomous Trust for Web Services
M. Coetzee and J.H.P. Eloff (South Africa)

Coffee/Tea Break

Session 2 : Networks [10:45 - 12:25]
Chair : Vic Grout

A Novel Security Protocol Enhancement on Distributed Multicasting for Video on Demand
P.E. Fouliras and V.A. Katos (Greece, UK)

TCP Performance Estimation Using Neural Networks Modelling
B.V. Ghita, S.M. Furnell, B. Lines and E. Ifeachor (UK, Australia)

Bottleneck-Queue Behavior: How much can TCP know about it?
L. Mamatras, V. Tsaoussidis and C. Zhang (Greece, USA)

The Connection Dependent Threshold in a fixed routing network
I.D. Moscholios and M.D. Logothetis (Greece)

Session 2 : Special Session [10:45 - 12:25]
Image, Signal and Distributed Data Processing
for Networked eHealth Applications
Chair : Ilias Maglogiannis

Knowledge Based Unification of Medical Archives
C. Diou, M. Falelakis and A. Delopoulos (Greece)

Scalable Medical Image Compression and Transmission on Mobile Devices using Wavelet Transform with ROI coding
C. Doukas, V. Moulos, G. Vafiadis, I. Maglogiannis and G. Kormentzas (Greece)

InUbiHealth: Intelligent Artefacts for Ubiquitous Health Monitoring
N. Tsapatsoulis and D. Vogiatzis (Cyprus)

A Review of Ad Hoc Networks for e-Health Applications
D.D. Vergados, G. Stergiou, I. Maglogiannis and A. Rouskas (Greece)

Lunch Break – LOCATION

Session 3 : Web Technologies [14:00 - 15:40]
Chair : Steven Furnell

Automatic Navigability Testing System for the Web: An Agent-based Approach
M. González, M. González, A. Puente and J. Manrubia (Spain)

Applying the Semantic Web to the Domain of Software Development
M.P. Evans, D. Griffiths and T. Putnam (UK)

Polar: Proxies collaborating to achieve anonymous web browsing
H. Tillwick, T. Neumann, M.S. Olivier, H.S. Venter and J.H.P. Eloff (South Africa)

An intelligent tutoring system for online self learning : a multi agent approach
O. Labouidya, N. Elkamoun, H. Benabdillah and A. Berraissoul (Morocco)

Session 3 : Special Session [14:00 - 15:40]
**Image, Signal and Distributed Data Processing
for Networked eHealth Applications**
Chair : Ilias Maglogiannis

Implementation of a jabber-based medical tele-consulting application
I.A. Sachpazidis , O. Hohlfeld and R. Ohl (Germany)

An Integrated Teleconsultation System for the Evaluation of the Risk of Stroke
E. Kyriacou, C. Pattichis, C. Christodoulou, M. Karaolis and A. Nicolaides (Cyprus, UK)

Integrating clinical information repositories: A framework for distributed analysis of
medical image data
V. Megalooikonomou and D. Kontos (USA)

Wavelet-based Mammographic Enhancement
H. Stefanou, S. Kakouros, D. Cavouras and M. Wallace (Greece)

15:40-16:00

Closing Ceremony & Announcing INC2006

End of Conference

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

INC 2006

Organised by the Network Research Group, University of Plymouth

www.inc2006.org